

MANAGEMENT OF MEDICAL DEVICES – A NOVEL APPROACH TO MODELLING DEMAND AND CAPACITY

Author(s)*: Mihaela BARDAN

Position: PhD Student

University: "Gh. Asachi" Technical University of Iasi, RO

Address: Bulevardul Profesor Dimitrie Mangeron 67, Iași 700050, RO

Email: elabardan@gmail.com

Webpage: www.tuiasi.ro

Abstract

Purpose – The aim of this research was to explore the potential of a novel approach to modelling medical device demand and capacity, called mission criticality.

Methodology/approach - Considered two possible techniques. One is based on the amount of time a medical device is used during a certain procedure, and the other is considering the availability of the same type of an equipment used in procedures done concurrently within the clinic.

Findings – It is believed that modelling the mission criticality of medical devices was achieved for one clinical procedures, and based on the probability densities of the procedural demand, a lack of vital monitoring devices was identified, and also an excess in the dialysis chairs' availability.

Research limitations/implications – Challenges may arise if clinical procedures are done outside one area of study, therefore, future work will need the development of a more sophisticated model.

Practical implications – Following this analysis, a review of the equipment management strategy was recommended as this could lead to a more effective use of the current available medical devices.

Originality/value – In the UK, this new opportunity to model the mission criticality of medical devices has emerged in the form of structured data on clinical procedures, the 'clinical coding data'.

Key words: Management of Medical Equipment, Clinical Engineering, Demand, Capacity.

Introduction

Modern healthcare is highly dependent on medical technology.

Efficient management of medical devices is an important part of delivering quality care, with the emphasis on safety as any failures in their performance may lead to an unacceptable risk of patient injury.

As a result, there is a widely recognised need to manage medical equipment effectively (MHRA, 2015). National and international guidelines and regulations have aimed to assist healthcare organisations in business planning, for the provision of a sufficient medical device inventory to safely meet a service user's needs (PHE, 2010) – however, there is a lack of precise guidance on how to manage, measure, and understand medical device demand and availability.

In literature there has been an ongoing development of management strategies and different models have been made available. However, it looks as if in current maintenance approaches, very little is known about medical device usage in certain clinical procedures; and currently there is no real understanding or any tool that can quantify the medical device demand.

Therefore, in existing approaches to business planning, management of medical device usage is only considered in general terms, and using broad, heuristic assumptions. Very little is quantified or understood about the level of medical device usage in practice and the 'one-size-fits-all' approaches inevitably result in waste. Without more information, the resourcing of medical technological infrastructure cannot be optimal.

Managing demand and service capacity has always been a controversial topic in all domains and relating the two has proven to be a challenge. The literature has offered many theoretical and empirical models to help with the decision taking process in the management of demand and capacity. The limitations in capacity come from the rather constant resources: the human and the capital one. The later includes accessibility to medical devices to perform clinical procedures. Demand, on the other hand, is not as straightforward to model as capacity. Although the flow of demand varies from service to service, as for instance, an outpatient clinic could theoretically manage and analyse its demands through patients' appointments; other services, such as the Accident and Emergency or Acute Services, have a potential unlimited demand which has long been considered to be more of an excess demand rather than a fluctuating one (Laing & Shiroyama, 1995).

Unpredictably, the financial strain on health organisations has not lead to a decline in purchasing medical devices. For instance, at Guy's and St Thomas' NHS Foundation Trust in London (GSTT) the number of equipment purchased has still increased within 2015-16 financial year whilst the number of medical equipment decommissioned has stagnated.

On the premises that there needs to be better signaling between medical device demand and the commitment to allocate financial resources for the procurement of additional medical equipment, it is questionable whether the health organisations need to buy more and more equipment. Therefore, this projects reflected on whether or not there is a realistic demand that the current capacity within GSTT was not meeting.

It was considered that through the understanding of the clinical coding data, focusing on the valuable information it contains on clinical procedures, a realistic model on medical device management demand could be built.

Modelling of the medical device demand and capacity will have a direct impact on the effectiveness of equipment management, and on equipment replacement plans; as decisions can become evidence based.

Approach

The aim of this research was to explore the potential of a novel approach to modelling medical device demand and capacity using data in Borough Kidney Treatment Centre (BKTC) within GSTT.

The approach analysed the demand and capacity separately and then, based on the findings, to comprehend the relationship between them and what they mean in combination. For instance, this type of analysis can give an indication about which resources the organisation is most dependent on.

The project intended to research the number of clinical procedures in specific facilities within GSTT's Borough Kidney Treatment Centre; and what medical devices were used for a specific procedure, XC40.3 Haemodialysis. The procedure involves a vital sign check before the haemodialysis process. The most recurrent medical devices involved in this clinical procedure include: Haemodialysis Chair, Haemodialysis Machine - for dialysis & recording the blood sugar, Non-Invasive Blood Pressure Monitor, SPO2 Monitor, and Thermometer.

The hypothesis of this study was that by understanding the retrospective relationship between medical equipment availability and clinical capacity, the mission criticality of medical devices could be quantified leading to effective procurement strategies and effective prioritisation of scheduled maintenance. The analysis of this data would enable an understanding on how the demand varies within a department on a weekly or a monthly basis. Methods such as probability densities have been considered in this report.

The clinical procedural demand data has been plotted individually; thus, enabling trends to be analysed more efficiently. Procedural demand would be related to medical device demand, using procedural models. In each procedural model, the duration of use of each medical device would be defined; this approximates the actual utilisation time for the medical equipment. Further analysis of the trend should indicate the quantity of medical devices required in a department to meet the clinical procedural demand.

To measure the uncertainty in demand it was considered to plot the data using kernel density estimators (KDE) used to estimate the probability distribution of the random variable based on a sample of points

taken from that distribution. It is a smoothed nonparametric representation. Unlike histograms where the data is placed in discrete bins making it discontinuous, the kernel function produces a smooth and continuous probability curve by summing up individual probability density curves for each data value.

Figure 1. Different representations of the X40.3 procedural demand within BKTC - Haemodialysis unfiltered data. Haemodialysis procedural demand on a daily, week and month basis (blue, black and red respectively). The data used to plot these procedures is not filtered and it is based on raw data extracted from the clinical coding data. Daily basis procedures, as shown above, are less predictable; hence, in real terms it is easier to plan for a week rather than for a day. Planning on a monthly basis would also be less efficient either as important fluctuations in demand can be missed. Also, the daily procedural demand plotted does not contain the Sunday's data as the clinic does not run on Sundays.

To model medical device capacity within GSTT, the data was extracted from the Medical Devices Assessment Management System - MDAM. To determine the capacity of a particular medical device within GSTT, information on the assets, job management and library loans have been extracted from MDAM and analysed in MATLAB. With the focus on the X40.3 Haemodialysis procedure within BKTC, the interviews with the clinicians have dedicated on how the procedure is executed and how long each step takes in order to build the modelling assumptions. Medical device capacity does not refer only to the number of medical devices available within the department, but also to their availability at a certain time. For example, whilst the haemodialysis machines are used for the entire length of the X40.3 procedure; hence, between 3 to 5 hours; the NIBP machine is used for two minutes only. However, the use of the NIBP machine is needed before the start of the procedure; hence, a milestone in the procedure's steps. Investigating the availability of the NIBP, SPO2, and Thermometers could turn out to be more complex as their availability is required at certain times. Although the number of dialysis machines has been consistent within BKTC, the maintenance of the devices has led to a variation in their availability. The maintenance can include planned maintenance, repairs, or quality control jobs. The lowest number of available haemodialysis machines has been recorded in week 130 with only 11 devices available. Analysing the data daily, the lowest availability is reached twice on consecutive days: day 902 and 903, day 909 and 910. These periods are days when the clinic was actively running and this represents a concern in meeting the procedural demand.

Figure 2. Availability of the other types of medical devices used in the X40.3 using unfiltered data

The availability of medical devices can be sub-categorised in equally important sub factors, such as the number of medical devices and availability at a certain time frame. Therefore, for the modelling of the mission criticality it has been considered two possible techniques. One is based on the amount of time a medical device is used during a certain procedure, and the other is considering the availability of a medical device for concurrent similar medical procedures.

THE TIME USAGE APPROACH: In this technique it has been taken into consideration the duration of the X40.3 clinical procedure – Haemodialysis. In the model, the procedure was estimated to take a maximum time of 5 hours, which included the patient greeting, initial observations, the procedure itself and the end of treatment.

Figure 3. Time usage model of demand and capacity for X40.3 Haemodialysis procedure and medical devices used for the entire length of the clinical procedure.

THE CONCURRENT PROCEDURES APPROACH: Whilst the time usage approach to model mission criticality looked at the total hours of medical device capacity, this approach takes into consideration the availability of medical devices in concurrent alike medical procedures.

Figure 4 - analysis of concurrent capacity and demand for NIBP, pulse oximeters and thermometers. Bottom: analysis of concurrent capacity and demand for HMD and dialysis chairs.

Similarly as in the previous approach in modelling mission criticality, the number of available haemodialysis machines do not always meet demand and in the worst case scenario only 62% of the demand is met. On the other hand, as the maximum amount of concurrent procedures is 33, it is highly probable that the dialysis chairs availability will meet the demand by 150%.

In regards to devices that are used for a shorter period of time, but simultaneously, the kernel density estimators are easier to analyse than previously, as Figure 4 shows. It is therefore clear there is a shortage in the medical devices used for vital signs monitoring.

To have accurate information on what medical devices were needed and for how long they are used in each episode of care, meetings with clinical staff are essential.

The future of an increased computational power to avoid human errors, and taking management decisions based on objective data rather than heuristically is not distant any longer.

Discussion and conclusions

Although, arguably observational studies for each individual clinical procedure can be undertaken, this would be a labour intensive approach and is not practically feasible; hence, this research that relied on modelling assumptions to define the mission criticality.

It is believed that the modelling of the mission criticality of medical devices has been achieved for the Borough Kidney Treatment Centre (BKTC) as a lack of vital monitoring devices has been identified, but also an excess in dialysis chairs availability.

Therefore, the medical device demand has realistically been quantified using clinical procedures and matched against the GSTT's asset inventory.

It is believed that following the modelling of this mission criticality, a review of the equipment management strategy within BKTC can lead to a more effective use of the current available medical devices.

For instance, because the availability of haemodialysis machines is highly variable due to planned maintenance, repair or quality control jobs and not the total asset number, it may be useful to evaluate the current procedures as these may cause bottle necks that lead to a high breakdown time. This may reveal that technicians need additional training, or that there is a delay in the delivery of spare parts. Optimising the availability time of the haemodialysis machines not only ensures demand is met, but also it can lead to the undertaking of more clinical procedures; hence, more episodes of care for patients.

On the other hand, the information on the shortage of the vital signs monitoring devices, such as the pulse oximeters or NIBPs, can be used in future capital investment planning by purchasing medical equipment based this objective data.

The statistics on the excess of the dialysis chairs can be used to reallocate these to other renal units within GSTT; therefore, taking maximum advantage of the current inventory without spending additional resources.

The objective has been to model mission criticality based on combining a quantified medical device demand with the current capacity, to better understand the medical device needs within GSTT. This has been done by analysing data for specific medical devices, based on the probabilistic modelling of their demand and capacity, and then the data on the volume of loans from the equipment library has been introduced.

It is believed that the project's objective to model mission criticality based on a realistic medical device demand with the current capacity was achieved. A lack of vital monitoring devices has been identified, but also an excess in dialysis chairs availability. Therefore, the medical device demand has realistically been quantified using clinical procedures and matched against the GSTT's asset inventory. Following the modelling of this mission criticality, a review of the equipment management strategy within BKTC can lead to a more effective use of the current available medical devices

Although, the paper presents a model for one department only this can be applied to other areas. Challenging may arise if clinical procedures are done outside the area of study, therefore future work will lead to the development of more sophisticated models applicable to other organisations, identify bottlenecks and also serve as evidence if an intervention should be considered.

The domino effect of the theory behind this project, would give access to valuable information for strategic management within GSTT and not only. Areas covered would include procurement of medical devices, replacement planning of equipment and even prioritisation of planned maintenance schedules.

Also, even though the clinical coding data is not currently error free for any of the Trusts in the UK, there is a strong financial incentive to improve it. This also applies to medical devices databases.

It is essential to highlight that the current healthcare is not going to necessarily improve if an investment to purchase more medical devices is made. The resources already available may not be used wisely. Modelling mission criticality using a quantified medical device demand and real capacity endeavours to shed light on this, identify bottlenecks and also serve as evidence if an investment should be considered.

Although GS1 (Global Standards 1) standardisation is currently under trial, the possibility in the far future to follow a patient's pathway through the health organisation can lead to a breakthrough in the analysis of use and management of medical devices.

In future work the clinical procedural data can be improved if combined with data from network connectivity if any available. For example, in GSTT there is worthy information on glucose meters connectivity and their use within the wards.

The future of an increased computational power to avoid human errors, and taking management decisions based on objective data rather than heuristically is not distant any longer.

Acknowledgement

This research was supported by the Clinical Engineering Department at Guy's and St Thomas' NHS Foundation Trust in London UK and King's College London.

References

DH, Department of Health

2002

Reforming NHS financial Flows: introducing payment by results. [Online]

Available at: www.gov.uk/dh

[Last accessed 14th July 2020].

Laing, A. & Shiroyama, C.,

1995.

Managing capacity and demand in a resource constrained environment: lessons for the NHS. *Journal of Management in Medicine*, 9(5), pp. 51 - 67.

MDD Medical Devices Directive,

1993

s.l.: European Parliament and of the Council of European Communities.

MHRA, Medicines and Healthcare Products Regulatory Agency - Managing Medical Devices

2015

Guidance for healthcare and social services organisations. [Online]

Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/>

[Last accessed 12 July 2020].

PHE, The Health and Social Care Act 2008 (Regulated Activities). [Online]

2010

Available at: www.legislation.gov.uk

[Last accessed 31 March 2016].

Taghipour, S., Banjevic, D. & Jardine, A.,

2011

Prioritization of medical equipment for maintenance decisions. *The Journal of the Operational Research Society*, 62(9), pp. 1666-1687.

The MathWorks, Inc.,

2015

MATLAB and Statistics Toolbox Release 2015b, Natick. Massachusetts, United States: s.n.

Wilson, K., Ison, K. & Tabakov, S.,

2014

Medical Equipment Management. s.l.:CRC Press.